

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Impact on the profitability of potato crops in Galicia from using decision-support systems

Assessing the economic impact of more sustainable agricultural practices is key to determining their feasibility and encouraging their adoption by farmers. This study analyzes the impact of using a predictive model to control Mildiu on the profitability of potato production compared to conventional systems, where fungicides are applied on a scheduled basis.

Three management strategies were evaluated over a three-year potato-wheat-potato cycle: (1) conventional, with fungicide applications every 7-10 days; (2) pest-alert system, with treatments based on the predictive model; and (3) no fungicides. The results show that the pest alert system reduces production costs by 7%, thanks to the lower use of fungicides and the reduction of associated agricultural tasks, such as the use of tractors. However, this reduction in fungicide use has a

negative impact on yields and leads to a 40% decrease in gross margin compared to conventional farming.

These results suggest that predictive models are a more environmentally sustainable option for controlling diseases such as Mildiu, but their profitability remains a challenge compared to conventional systems, which offer higher yields and greater economic stability. However, the large differences observed throughout the cycle analyzed underscore the need to evaluate these practices over longer periods of time to more robustly confirm these results. With this information, farmers can make informed decisions about implementing these models and optimizing integrated management strategies to maintain high levels of productivity.

1. Graph showing how gross margins vary according to the different agricultural practices used. It illustrates the overall distribution of the data obtained, including the most frequent values (shaded box), the mean value (black line), and the extreme values (highest and lowest values).

	Direct costs (€/ha)	Sales revenue (€/ha)	Gross margin (€/ha)
T1: Conventional	14,544	24,238	12,603
T2: Pest alert system	13,287	18,539	7,476
T3: No fungicides	12,528	15,340	4,652

2. Average value of production costs, sales revenues, and gross margins, calculated for each practice analysed in a 3-year rotation (potato-wheat-potato).

KEYWORDS

Economic profitability, gross margin, pest alert system, potato cultivation, predictive model, fungicides

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